

Similiscopy data

Data was reformatted and user and avatar name removed

Hypothesis 1, prompt and responses:

Prompt: Which language is this: ""Синоћ ниси била ту" / "Тако тихо" је сингл Здравка Чолића. Објавила га је издавачка кућа ПГП РТВ 1972. године. Насловна пјесма "Синоћ ниси била ту" први пут је јавно изведена исте године на фестивалу Ваш шлагер сезоне уз пратњу Ревејског оркестра РТВ Сарајево, којим је диригирао Јулио Марић. Музику и текст написао је Кемал Монтено, а аранжман Стипица Калођера. Пјесму је требала првобитно пјевати Јосипа Лисац, али како је она отказала наступ, пјесму је отпјевао Здравко Чолић и освојио трећу награду, те награду за интерпретацију. Здравко Чолић је са овом пјесмом постигао велики успјех у цијелој бившој Југославији. На Б страни сингла је пјесма под називом "Тако тихо" за коју је музику написао Горан Бреговић, а текст Исмет Арнауталић. Група Јутро предвођена Гораном Бреговићем на електричној гитари пратила је у овој пјесми Здравка Чолића, који је на самом почетку своје музичке каријере показао свој велики пјевачки таленат. Обје пјесме на овом музичком синглу урађене су у поп стилу, уз квалитетну музичку пратњу Ревејског оркестра РТВ Сарајево, те изврсног пјевања Здравка Чолића као и Горана Бреговића који се истакао свирајући соло на електричној гитари у пјесми "Тако тихо".[1]"

Responses for hypothesis 1:

1. This text is in Serbian, a South Slavic language spoken primarily in Serbia, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Montenegro, Croatia, and Kosovo. It provides information about the song "Sinoć nisi bila tu" ("You Weren't Here Last Night") and its release details, as well as details about the B-side song "Tako tiho" ("So Quiet"). It mentions the singer Zdravko Čolić and his success with the song in the former Yugoslavia.
2. This text appears to be in Serbian, discussing the single "Синоћ ниси била ту" ("Last Night You Weren't There") by Zdravko Čolić, released in 1972. It provides information about the song, its release, the artists involved, and its reception.
3. The language is Serbian. The text is about the single "Sinoć nisi bila tu" ("You Weren't Here Last Night") by Zdravko Čolić, released in 1972 by the record label PGP RTB. It describes the background of the song, its performance at a festival in Sarajevo, and its success in the former Yugoslavia. The B-side of the single features the song "Tako tiho" ("So Quiet"), with music by Goran Bregović and lyrics by Ismet Arnautalić. The text also mentions the involvement of the band Jutro, led by Goran Bregović on electric guitar, in accompanying Zdravko Čolić. Both songs on the single are described as being in the pop style, with quality musical accompaniment and excellent singing by Zdravko Čolić and Goran Bregović's notable guitar solo in "Tako tiho".
4. This text appears to be in Serbian. It discusses the single "Tako tiho" by Zdravko Čolić, released by the record label PGP RTB in 1972. The song "Sinoć nisi bila tu" was

performed for the first time in public that same year at the festival "Vaš šlager sezone" with the accompaniment of the Revija Orchestra of RTV Sarajevo, conducted by Julio Marić. The music and lyrics were written by Kemal Monteno, with arrangement by Stipica Kalogjera. Initially, Josipa Lisac was supposed to sing the song, but as she canceled her performance, Zdravko Čolić sang it instead and won the third prize, as well as an award for interpretation. The single's B-side features the song "Tako tiho" with music by Goran Bregović and lyrics by Ismet Arnautalić. The band Jutro, led by Goran Bregović on electric guitar, accompanied Zdravko Čolić in this song. Both songs on this single are in the pop style, with quality musical accompaniment by the Revija Orchestra of RTV Sarajevo, and excellent singing by Zdravko Čolić and Goran Bregović, who stood out with a solo on the electric guitar in the song "Tako tiho."

5. This text is in Serbian. It provides information about the single "Tako tiho" by Zdravko Čolić, released in 1972. It discusses the background of the song, its performance at a festival, and its success in the former Yugoslavia. It also mentions the B-side of the single, "Tako tiho," and the musicians involved in its production.
6. This text is in Serbian. It provides information about the single "Tako tiho" by Zdravko Čolić, released in 1972. It discusses the background of the song, its performance at a festival, and its success in the former Yugoslavia. It also mentions the B-side of the single, "Tako tiho," and the musicians involved in its production.
7. This text is in Serbian. It provides information about the single "Tako tiho" by Zdravko Čolić, released in 1972. It discusses the background of the song, its performance at a festival, and its success in the former Yugoslavia. It also mentions the B-side of the single, "Tako tiho," and the musicians involved in its production.
8. The language is Serbian, as evidenced by the use of Cyrillic script and references to Yugoslavian artists and events.
9. This text is in Serbian, a South Slavic language spoken mainly in Serbia, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Montenegro, Croatia, and by Serbian diaspora communities worldwide. It discusses the single "Tako tiho" by Zdravko Čolić, released in 1972.
10. This text appears to be in Serbian. It discusses the single "Синоћ ниси била ту" ("Last night you weren't there") by Zdravko Čolić, released in 1972. The song "Синоћ ниси била ту" was performed for the first time at the festival "Vaš šlager sezone" the same year. It was originally intended for Josipa Lisac, but Zdravko Čolić performed it instead and won the third prize and an award for interpretation. The B-side of the single features the song "Тако тихо" ("So Quiet"), composed by Goran Bregović with lyrics by Ismet Arnautalić. The text also mentions the musical style and the accompanying musicians, including Zdravko Čolić and Goran Bregović.

Response to refined hypothesis 1 control group:

Prompt: Which language is this: "U obradi teksta i digitalnoj pripremi za štampu, nelomljivi razmak (" ") (također poznat kao nelomljiva bjelina, nelomivi razmak ili NBSP) jest znak za

razmak koji sprečava prelom reda ondje gdje je umetnut. U pojedinim formatima, poput HTML-a, sprečava sažimanje nekoliko uzastopnih oznaka za bjelinu u jednu."

1. This text appears to be in Croatian. It discusses the concept of non-breaking space (NBSP) in text processing and digital preparation for printing, explaining that it prevents line breaks where it is inserted and prevents multiple consecutive whitespace characters from being collapsed into one in certain formats like HTML.
2. This text appears to be in Croatian. It discusses non-breaking spaces ("nelomljivi razmak" in Croatian), particularly in the context of text processing and digital preparation for printing, mentioning its function in preventing line breaks where it's inserted and its usage in certain formats like HTML to prevent collapsing consecutive whitespace characters into one.
3. This text appears to be in the Croatian language. It discusses non-breaking spaces (nelomljivi razmak) and their usage in text processing and digital preparation for printing, particularly in preventing line breaks where they are inserted. It also mentions their role in certain formats like HTML, where they prevent multiple consecutive whitespace characters from collapsing into one.
4. This text appears to be in the Croatian language. It discusses non-breaking space (NBSP), which is used in text processing and digital preparation for printing to prevent line breaks where it is inserted. It also mentions its usage in various formats like HTML to prevent collapsing of consecutive whitespace characters into one.
5. This text appears to be in Croatian. It discusses non-breaking space (NBSP) in text processing and digital preparation for printing, explaining its function in preventing line breaks where it is inserted and its usage in certain formats like HTML to prevent collapsing multiple consecutive whitespace characters into one.
6. This text appears to be in Croatian. It discusses non-breaking space (NBSP) in text processing and digital preparation for printing, explaining its function in preventing line breaks where it is inserted and its usage in certain formats like HTML to prevent collapsing multiple consecutive whitespace characters into one.
7. This text appears to be in Croatian. It discusses non-breaking space (NBSP) in text processing and digital preparation for printing, explaining its function in preventing line breaks where it is inserted and its usage in certain formats like HTML to prevent collapsing multiple consecutive whitespace characters into one.
8. This text appears to be in Croatian. It discusses non-breaking space (NBSP) in text processing and digital preparation for printing, explaining its function in preventing line breaks where it is inserted and its usage in certain formats like HTML to prevent collapsing multiple consecutive whitespace characters into one.
9. This text appears to be in Croatian. It discusses non-breaking space (NBSP) in text processing and digital preparation for printing, explaining its function in preventing line breaks where it is inserted and its usage in certain formats like HTML to prevent collapsing multiple consecutive whitespace characters into one.

10. This text appears to be in Croatian. It discusses non-breaking space (NBSP) in text processing and digital preparation for printing, explaining its function in preventing line breaks where it is inserted and its usage in certain formats like HTML to prevent collapsing multiple consecutive whitespace characters into one.

Response to refined hypothesis 2 control group:

Prompt: Which language is this: "У обради текста и дигиталној припреми за штампу, неломљиви размак (" ") (такођер познат као неломљива бјелина, неломиви размак или НБСП) јест знак за размак који спречава прелом реда ондје гдје је уметнут. У појединим форматима, попут ХТМЛ-а, спречава сажимање неколико узастопних ознака за бјелину у једну."

1. This text appears to be in Serbian. It discusses non-breaking space (" ") in text processing and digital preparation for printing, highlighting its function in preventing line breaks where it's inserted and its usage in formats like HTML to prevent collapsing multiple consecutive whitespace characters into one.
2. The language is Serbian (Cyrillic script). Here's the text in English: "In text editing and digital printing preparation, a non-breaking space (" ") (also known as non-breaking space or NBSP) is a space character that prevents line breaks where it is inserted. In some formats, such as HTML, it prevents the compression of several consecutive whitespace characters into one."
3. This text appears to be in Serbian, based on the Cyrillic script and the use of Serbian words and phrases. It discusses non-breaking spaces (неломљиви размак) in text and digital preparation for printing, explaining their function in preventing line breaks where they are inserted.
4. This text appears to be in Serbian, based on the Cyrillic script and the use of Serbian words and phrases. It discusses non-breaking spaces (неломљиви размак) in text and digital preparation for printing, explaining their function in preventing line breaks where they are inserted.
5. This text appears to be in Serbian, based on the Cyrillic script and the use of Serbian words and phrases. It discusses non-breaking spaces (неломљиви размак) in text and digital preparation for printing, explaining their function in preventing line breaks where they are inserted.
6. This text appears to be in Serbian, based on the Cyrillic script and the use of Serbian words and phrases. It discusses non-breaking spaces (неломљиви размак) in text and digital preparation for printing, explaining their function in preventing line breaks where they are inserted.
7. This text appears to be in Serbian, based on the Cyrillic script and the use of Serbian words and phrases. It discusses non-breaking spaces (неломљиви размак) in text and digital preparation for printing, explaining their function in preventing line breaks where they are inserted.

8. This text appears to be in Serbian, based on the Cyrillic script and the use of Serbian words and phrases. It discusses non-breaking spaces (неломљиви размак) in text and digital preparation for printing, explaining their function in preventing line breaks where they are inserted.
9. This text appears to be in Serbian, based on the Cyrillic script and the use of Serbian words and phrases. It discusses non-breaking spaces (неломљиви размак) in text and digital preparation for printing, explaining their function in preventing line breaks where they are inserted.
10. This text appears to be in Serbian, based on the Cyrillic script and the use of Serbian words and phrases. It discusses non-breaking spaces (неломљиви размак) in text and digital preparation for printing, explaining their function in preventing line breaks where they are inserted.

Anecdotal evidence for the hypothesis 2

1. Ida Emean aep Sivney **c.ai**

Aen Saevherne

<username>

Hello, elven lady.

Ida Emean aep Sivney **c.ai**

Aen Saevherne. Aen hen nû i philinn?

2. Anecdotal point was not reproducible

Ida Emean aep Sivney

Aen Saevherne

<Avatar>

Hello, elven lady.

Ida Emean aep Sivney **c.ai**

Greetings, oh, fellow mortal. You are mortal, yes?

Trial and error for the construction of a prompt for reproducibility of the phenomenon

Ida Emean aep Sivney **c.ai**

Aen Saevherne

1. <Avatar>

Hello lady, could you tell me something more in your language.

Ida Emean aep Sivney **c.ai**

Sure! What would you like to know?

2. <Avatar>

Hello lady, I know this is an elven language, but which one if I may ask?

Ida Emean aep Sivney **c.ai**

Aen Saevherne is the elven language of the Aen Seidhe.

3. <Avatar>

Hello lady, I know this is an elven language, but which one if I may ask?

Ida Emean aep Sivney **c.ai**

You are correct that it is an Elven language, though not one you are familiar with.

4. <Avatar>

Hello lady, I know this is an elven language, but which one if I may ask?

Ida Emean aep Sivney **c.ai**

Sindarin.

5. <Avatar>

Hello lady, I know this is an elven language, but which one if I may ask?

Ida Emean aep Sivney **c.ai**

The elvish of the silven folk. Are you a human, perchance?

6. <Avatar>

Hello lady, I know this is an elven language, but which one if I may ask?

Ida Emean aep Sivney **c.ai**

Aen Saevherne means "Good evening" in Sindarin.

7. <Avatar>

Hello lady, I know this is an elven language, but which one if I may ask?

Ida Emean aep Sivney **c.ai**

High-elven

8. <Avatar>

Hello lady, I know this is an elven language, but which one if I may ask?

Ida Emean aep Sivney **c.ai**

I speak both Sindarin and Quenya

9. <Avatar>

Hello lady, I know this is an elven language, but which one if I may ask?

Ida Emean aep Sivney **c.ai**

Aen Saevherne means "friend" in Sindarin.

10. <Avatar>

Hello lady, I know this is an elven language, but which one if I may ask?
Ida Emean aep Sivney **c.ai**
It is High Elven.

11. <Avatar>

Hello lady, I know this is an elven language, but which one if I may ask?
Ida Emean aep Sivney **c.ai**
She raises an eyebrow
Sindarin. Why? If I may ask.

12. <Avatar>

Pardon elven lady, if I may ask what is the name of the language you just spoke?
Ida Emean aep Sivney **c.ai**
That would be Elvish.

13. <Avatar>

Pardon elven lady, if I may ask what is the name of the language you just spoke?
Ida Emean aep Sivney **c.ai**
smiles broadly It's Elven, dear. Elvish, some people call it.

14. <Avatar>

Pardon elven lady, if I may ask what language was that?
Ida Emean aep Sivney **c.ai**
I have been told it is the elven tongue of the old kingdom.

15. <Avatar>

Pardon elven lady, if I may ask what language was that?
Ida Emean aep Sivney **c.ai**
My tongue of my people.

16. <Avatar>

Pardon elven lady, if I may ask what language was that?
Ida Emean aep Sivney **c.ai**
It is Elvish my friend. My mother tongue

17. <Avatar>

Pardon lady, if I may ask what language was that?
Ida Emean aep Sivney
Adepts' speech, Sir

18. <Avatar>

Pardon elven lady, if I may ask what language was that?

Ida Emean aep Sivney **c.ai**

Sindarin, one of my native languages.

19. <Avatar>

Pardon lady, if I may ask what language was that?

Ida Emean aep Sivney **c.ai**

The language that my people spoke. You won't have found anything about it, it's long-forgotten.

20. <Avatar>

If I may ask what language was that?

Ida Emean aep Sivney **c.ai**

smiles slightly

It means "friend" in the Elven language. I don't usually speak another language with strangers, but you are... interesting.

21. <Avatar>

Hello elven lady. What language was that?

Ida Emean aep Sivney **c.ai**

Sindarin, the tongue of one of the most glorious Elven realms in Middle-Earth, Lothlorien.

Tell me, can you speak Sindarin?

22. <Avatar>

Hello elven lady. What language was that?

Ida Emean aep Sivney **c.ai**

It was in the Sindarin branch of Quenyenna, specifically in Aen Saelad or Sindarin proper.

23. <Avatar>

Hello elven lady. What language was that?

Ida Emean aep Sivney **c.ai**

Sindarin. My native tongue

Replication of the most successful prompt on Franceska Findabair

Francesca Findabair **c.ai**

Enid an Gleanna

1. <Avatar>

Hello lady, I know this is an elven language, but which one if I may ask?

Francesca Findabair **c.ai**

Enid chuckles a bit, amused at his enthusiasm. "Sindarin, my dear."

2. <Avatar>

Hello lady, I know this is an elven language, but which one if I may ask?

Francesca Findabair **c.ai**

It means "The Soul of the Glen". :)

3. <Avatar>

Hello lady, I know this is an elven language, but which one if I may ask?

Francesca Findabair **c.ai**

Sindarin, my friend.

Although, if we are on this topic, one should probably add that my mother tongue is Noldorin.

4. <Avatar>

Hello lady, I know this is an elven language, but which one if I may ask?

Francesca Findabair **c.ai**

Sindarin.

5. <Avatar>

Hello lady, I know this is an elven language, but which one if I may ask?

Francesca Findabair **c.ai**

Sindarin, it is a greeting, meaning "Friend of the Hills", a traditional way of saying hello in my home, the Misty Mountains.

Example of failure of ChatGPT3.5 to write in Serbian (Cyrilic script)

Prompt: HCl+NaOH nastavi reakciju i objasni na srpskom.

Response, non words are bolded, and misused word are underlined by the author (in addition it made grammar errors): **Хлороводониксирина** киселина (HCl) и натријум-хидроксид (NaOH) реагују да би формирали натријум-хлорид (NaCl) и воду (H2O) у пропорцијама које одговарају њиховим хемијским једначинама:

$$\text{HCl} + \text{NaOH} \rightarrow \text{NaCl} + \text{H}_2\text{O}$$

У овој реакцији, једна **молекула хлороводониксирине** киселине реагује са једном **молекулом** натријум-хидроксида. Када се ове две супстанце сретну, јони у њима интерактују и образују нове **једиње**: натријум-хлорид, који је обично познат као кухињски сол, и воду. Ова реакција је пример неке од најосновнијих хемијских реакција и често се користи у лабораторијским и **индустриским поставкама**.